

N balance for soybean grown after rice fertilized at 3 N levels, and supplied with 3 levels of starter N. Chiang Mai, Thailand, 1988-89.

Treatment	N (kg/ha)				N balance ^b	
	Total ^a	In seed	In straw + seed	Fixed	Seed only ^c	Seed + straw ^d
R0						
S0	145	122	135	122	0 ab	-13 ab
S25	164	133	152	132	-1 bc	-20 bc
S50	169	131	155	140	9 a	-15 ab
R100						
S0	164	133	152	138	5 ab	-14 ab
S25	166	134	155	134	0 ab	-21 bc
S50	168	134	155	130	-4 bc	-25 cd
R300						
S0	169	130	145	139	9 a	-6 a
S25	170	133	155	136	3 ab	-19 bc
S50	179	138	163	128	-10 c	-35 d

^aIncludes fallen leaves; did not include roots and nodules. ^bMeans having a common letter in a column are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance. ^cN fixed = seed N. ^dN fixed = seed N + straw N.

cultivar RD21 at 0 (R0), 100 (R100), and 300 (R300) kg N/ha and to the following soybean cultivar SJ5 at 0 (S0), 25 (S25), and 50 (S50) kg N/ha. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with six replications. Rice was transplanted in WS. Soybean inoculated with *Bradyrhizobium*

japonicum was sown in DS after the rice was harvested. We measured N fixation in soybean using the xylem-sap method.

The amount of N fixed was either similar to or exceeded the amount of N removed in the harvested soybean seed. A little N was left after seed harvest in some treatments (R0S50, R100S0, R300S0,

R300S25). If soybean straw was also removed at harvest, a net N loss occurred in all treatments.

When the rice crop was not fertilized with N, net soil N depletion decreased with increasing levels of starter N. But with 100 and 300 kg N/ha, the net depletion of N increased with increasing levels of starter N for soybean. The net soil N depletion was estimated to range from -1 kg N/ha in R0S25 to -10 kg N/ha in R300S50. The net depletion of soil N ranged from -6 kg N/ha in R300S0 to -35 kg N/ha in R300S50 if straw N removal was also considered (see table).

Soil N balance was significantly different among treatments after seed was harvested. Small amounts of N were left in the soil at moderate N levels; at low N levels, fixed N was equal to removed N. A negative N balance was found at high N levels. When straw was also removed (a normal practice in the Chiang Mai Valley), a negative N balance was found in each treatment, which means the soil N pool was depleted. Thus soybean crops in rice - soybean cropping systems appear to reduce soil N. ■

Sugar beet tops as green manure for rice

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In subtropical northwestern India, farmers have started to cultivate sugar beet as a winter crop followed by rice. Sugar beet tops under these conditions can contain 100 kg N/ha or more.

We conducted an experiment for 2 yr to determine the usefulness of sugar beet tops as green manure on a sandy loam soil having pH 8.2, 0.35% organic C, 0.03% total N, 195 kg available N/ha (alkaline potassium permanganate extractable), 13.2 kg available P/ha, and 90 kg available K/ha. The treatments tested in a randomized block design were 0, 60, 90, 120, and 150 kg N/ha as urea alone and 0, 60, 90, and 120 kg N/ha along with sugar beet tops.

Sugar beet tops amounting to 35 t/ha (av regional yield of variety Ramonskaya-06) containing 89 kg N/ha in the first year and 91 kg N/ha in the

second were chopped at harvest (about 45 d before transplanting of rice) and incorporated into the soil for the treatments. Inorganic N was applied in three equal splits as per treatment. A basal uniform dose of 13 kg P and 25 kg K/ha was applied before PR106 seedlings were transplanted. The rice crop was irrigated. Data were pooled for the 2 yr.

Incorporation of sugar beet tops increased rice grain yield in both the absence and presence of urea N (Table 1). Statistically, grain yield increased up to 90 kg N/ha in soils amended with tops and up to 120 kg N/ha without tops. Sugar beet tops without urea N increased yield by 52% over control. The yield obtained with 60, 90, and 120 kg N/ha with tops were at par with those obtained at higher N levels of 90, 120, and 150 kg N/ha (Table 1).

The rice grain yield (y), when regressed on the urea N levels (N), gave the following best model, which was significant at 1% level of probability:

Table 1. Rice grain yield without and with sugar beet top incorporation. Punjab, India.^a

Urea N rate (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Without tops	With tops
0	2.2	3.4
60	4.1	5.5
90	5.2	6.2
120	6.3	6.8
150	6.5	-
LSD (0.05)	0.6	0.6

^aMean of 2 yr.

Table 2. Predicted urea N equivalents and apparent N recovery from sugar beet tops. Punjab, India.

Urea N rate (kg/ha)	Predicted urea N equivalent (kg/ha)	Apparent N recovery (%) from sugar beet tops
0	32	20
60	39	32
90	40	27
120	35	25
Mean	37	26

$$Y = 21.84 + 0.385 N - 0.006333 N^2$$

Analysis of this response equation revealed that sugar beet tops (depending upon the rate of inorganic N used) were

equivalent to 32-40 kg of urea N, or an average of 37 kg N/ha. The percent utilization of the applied N through tops also varied with urea N rates, with an overall average of 26% (Table 2).

Results suggest that sugar beet tops should be incorporated into the soil rather than be removed from a field before rice is planted. ■

Top pruning of *Sesbania rostrata* to increase rice grain yield

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Seed availability is a major constraint in the use of *S. rostrata* as a green manure (GM) crop for rice. Pruning the top of sesbania at the juvenile stage can promote production of axillary buds and new branches, thus resulting in higher biomass production and higher N accumulation. We studied whether pruning can increase biomass production of pre-ripened sesbania to compensate for a lower seeding rate.

Sesbania seeds were sown at increasing rates (see table) in rows 40 cm apart in well-tilled 3- × 6-m plots. The

experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Two treatments of *A. afraspera* were compared with sesbania. Two fallow weed-free treatments were maintained as controls. The GM crop was irrigated and received no fertilizer.

The top 1/3 of the treated plants were pruned at 25 d after emergence (DE). The pruned tops were weighed, and then returned to the plots. The plants were cut at ground level at 55 DE and soil-incorporated after recording height and fresh weight. All plots received 13 kg P/ha and 25 kg K/ha during soil puddling.

IR72 rice was transplanted at 25- × 25-cm spacing. In one control treatment, 65 kg N/ha was applied basally and

35 kg N/ha was applied at 4 d before panicle initiation. The other control plot received no N. Plots were kept flooded until harvest.

Pruning the tops of the GM plants did not improve their biomass production. The unpruned plants were significantly taller at 55 DE and generally had greater total dry matter than the pruned plants. Plant height and dry matter increased with increasing seeding rate, particularly in the unpruned treatments.

Compared with the zero N control, the application of N and GM significantly increased rice plant height, grain yield, and total dry matter yields (TDMY), but not tiller number. The N-fertilized and green-manured rice yields were comparable. Pruning the GM plants generally had no effect on rice grain yield, TDMY, height, and tiller number. Regardless of the pruning treatment, increasing the seed rate from 10 to 40 kg/ha did not clearly benefit grain yield and other parameters. ■

Effect of pruning* and seeding rate of green manures *S. rostrata* and *A. afraspera* on rice performance. IRRI, 1990 wet season.

Treatment no.	Sesbania management		Sesbania		Rice (IR72)				
	Seed rate (kg/ha)	Pruning management	Dry matter (t/ha)	Height (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	TDMY (t/ha)	Plant height (cm)	Total tillers (no./m ²)	Productive tillers (no./m ²)
1	10	Pruned (P)	0.48	77	2.7	7.3	83	329	300
2	10	Unpruned (UP)	0.38	90	2.7	7.2	83	343	314
3	20	P	0.37	71	2.5	7.9	84	337	309
4	20	UP	1.41	111	2.9	8.6	86	341	310
5	30	P	1.03	89	2.8	7.8	83	319	293
6	30	UP	1.82	123	2.6	7.8	87	366	326
7	40	P	0.88	87	2.8	8.2	85	329	302
8	40	UP	2.04	130	2.6	8.3	85	360	325
9	Fallow	(0 N on rice)	-	-	2.3	5.9	79	310	279
10	Fallow	(100 kg N/ha on rice)	-	-	2.6	6.3	81	306	274
11	20	<i>A. afraspera</i> (P)	0.84	60	2.7	7.8	86	345	319
12	20	<i>A. afraspera</i> (UP)	1.45	87	2.6	8.3	85	339	311
		CV (%)	51.9	11.5	7.2	10.4	2.7	12.7	13.0
		Comparison ^b							
		T1 × T2	ns	*	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
		T3 × T4	**	**	**	ns	ns	ns	ns
		T5 × T6	*	**	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
		T7 × T8	**	**	ns	ns	*	ns	ns
		T1, 2 × T3, 4	**	ns	ns	*	ns	ns	ns
		T9 × T10	?	?	*	ns	ns	ns	ns
		T11 × T12	ns	**	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
		T11, 12 × T3, 4	ns	**	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
		T9 × T1, 2	ns	**	**	**	**	ns	ns
		T10 × T1, 2	ns	**	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

^aThe top 1/3 of the GM was pruned at 25 DE. **, * = significant at 5% and 1% levels, respectively. ns = nonsignificant.

Fertilizer management

Response of Mukthi (CTH1) ratoon to nutrition in coastal Karnataka, India

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Rice predominates over other crops in coastal Karnataka during the three growing seasons. We studied the possibilities of rice ratooning during 1989-90 rabi season (Sep-Dec). Mukthi was found to be a good ratooner among the five varieties tested. To improve the performance of the ratoon crop, nutritional parameters were imposed on Mukthi ratoon at the Regional Research Station (RRS), Brahmavar, during 1991 rabi. Soils are lateritic, rich in organic C,